

The Development of Bioethics in CIS and EAEU: General Overview

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Abstract: This article reviews current issues on bioethics in law. The author pays special attention to the system of human rights protection in bioethics within the post-soviet space such as CIS and EAEU. The regulation of bioethical issues within post-Soviet intergovernmental organizations remains underdeveloped. Initial steps have been taken within the CIS. However, the non-binding nature of these instruments limits their effectiveness. In contrast, the EAEU has not addressed human rights in its legal framework at all, and issues of bioethics remain entirely unregulated.

Keywords: human rights, genetic engineering, ethical values, Model Law, bioethics, CIS legislation, EAEU court.

The biotechnological revolution of the twentieth century catalyzed significant scientific advancements, notably in the domain of genetic engineering. Research in genetics has become fundamentally important from a scientific standpoint, yet it simultaneously prompts a range of anthropological, ethical, and related concerns. From a legal perspective, progress in biomedical sciences directly influences the full spectrum of human rights—particularly natural and personal rights—and extends to a relatively novel category of rights emerging within biomedicine and information technology. Consequently, the application of these rights gives rise to complex ethical and legal challenges.

In response to these dilemmas, the discipline of bioethics was established to address and reconcile such conflicts. The ethical principles formulated within this framework have subsequently been incorporated into legal regulations.

The term “bioethics” possesses both broad and narrow connotations. It was originally coined by the American biochemist Van Rensselaer Potter, who is credited with shaping the contemporary concept of bioethics. Potter defined bioethics as “the science of survival, encompassing not only human beings—with their physical and

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value dimensions—but also the entire living world”² within the scope of scientific inquiry. Conversely, American physician André Hellegers employed the term “bioethics” to denote the “interdisciplinary investigation of ethical issues arising within biomedicine, particularly those concerning the protection of patient dignity and rights”³. The Explanatory Note to the draft Declaration on Universal Norms in the Field of Bioethics proposed the following definition: bioethics is “the field of systematic, pluralistic, and interdisciplinary study and regulation of ethical issues emerging in medicine, life sciences, and social sciences related to humans and their interactions with the biosphere, including challenges associated with the availability and accessibility of scientific and technological advances and their applications”⁴.

An analysis of this definition reveals key characteristics of the bioethical approach. Primarily, bioethics is interdisciplinary, integrating perspectives from both medical and humanitarian disciplines to address complex issues. Additionally, it is inherently pluralistic, acknowledging that no single, universally accepted system of values or beliefs exists to resolve ethical conflicts. The emergence of bioethics is a direct consequence of scientific and technological progress, which has not only broadened the scope of biomedical possibilities but also reshaped traditional moral and ethical values. Consequently, fundamental concepts such as human dignity, beneficence, and harm have acquired new dimensions and significance.

These evolving ethical principles constitute the core content of bioethics. Among the various factors contributing to the formation of bioethics, the ecological concept plays a significant role, emphasizing the creation of conditions conducive to the favorable physical existence of humans. In this context, biomedicine has pursued not only the development of new, effective therapeutics but also the minimization of their adverse effects. Consequently, the interval between the development of a new drug and its clinical application has lengthened substantially. For example, “whereas in the early 1960s this period spanned only a few weeks, by the early 1980s it had extended to approximately ten years, accompanied by a twentyfold or greater increase in development costs”⁵. This shift underscores the prioritization of safety as a critical metric in medical practice.

Subsequently, the ecological concept was supplanted by a human rights framework, which redirected biomedical ethics toward a new trajectory. The legal dimension emphasized not merely the prevention of threats to human well-being but the articulation of human moral identity amid advancing medical technologies. As humans are the primary focus of medicine, they inherently become subjects of scientific research. Initially, the prevailing view within the medical community posited that individual human life was subordinate to the common good served by biomedical research⁶, a stance that ultimately provoked significant public debate. Consequently, by the early 1960s, this paradigm shifted toward recognizing patients as autonomous individuals capable of making independent medical decisions. The principle of personal autonomy became foundational, and biomedical research could no longer proceed without the voluntary, informed consent of the participant.

² Potter, V. R. *Bioethics: A Bridge to the Future* / V. R. Potter; translated from English / edited by S. V. Vekovishina, V. L. Kulichenko. – K.: Publisher Karpenko V. M., 2002, p. 48.

³ *Bioethics: principles, rules, problems.* – Ed. by B.G. Yudin. Moscow, Editorial URSS, 1998, p. 32.

⁴ Explanatory note on the development of a preliminary draft declaration on universal norms in the field of bioethics // UNESDOC URL: https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000139586_rus (accessed on 13 May 2024).

⁵ Tishchenko, P.D. *Philosophy of Morality and Bioethics (Reflections on the Report by A.A. Guseinov)* / Humanitarian Bulletin of L.N. Tolstoy TSPU. 2019. No. 2 (30), p. 134.

⁶ See, for example, Jay Katz. *The Regulation of Human Experimentation in the United States – A Personal Odyssey* // *IRB: A Review of Human Subject Research* vol. 9, Number 1, pp.1–6.

The System of Human Rights Protection in Bioethics within the Post-Soviet Space: CIS and EAEU

The Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) is a regional international organization encompassing countries of the post-Soviet space, including Russia and eight other member states. Established to foster comprehensive cooperation, economic integration, human rights protection, and mutual assistance, the CIS has progressively engaged in regulating and safeguarding human rights in the domain of bioethics.

Within the framework of the World Health Organization's "Strategic Initiative for the Development of Ethical Expertise," five regional forums were established, among which is the Forum of Ethics Committees of the CIS Member States (FECIS). Founded in 2001 following a resolution by an international conference of ethics committee representatives from CIS countries, FECIS has played a pivotal role in advancing bioethical discourse and practice across the region. The primary objective of the Forum was to facilitate the development of bioethics within CIS member states and to establish harmonized collaboration, particularly concerning ethical standards in biomedical research involving human subjects.

In pursuit of this goal, the Forum of Ethics Committees of the CIS Member States (FECIS) engaged in active cooperation with the Standing Committee of the CIS Interparliamentary Assembly on Social Policy and Human Rights, as well as the Standing Committee on Science and Education. This collaborative framework enabled a comprehensive review of relevant documents from multiple perspectives, the conduction of analytical consultations, and ultimately, the endorsement of model legislative acts.

As a direct outcome, in 2005, the Interparliamentary Assembly of CIS Member States adopted the Model Law "On the Protection of Human Rights and Dignity in Biomedical Research in CIS Member States" (hereinafter, the Model Law). This legislation established a foundational framework for inter-state cooperation in bioethics and sought to safeguard human rights and dignity within the context of biomedical research. Notably, the Model Law's preamble references international instruments of universal bioethical regulation, underscoring its alignment with globally recognized standards.

The most fundamental principles governing biomedical research are articulated in Article 4 of the Model Law: "Biomedical research shall be conducted with the primary aim of generating new knowledge to improve biomedical practice and only when no alternative means exist to obtain such knowledge; the rights and interests of human subjects shall take precedence over those of society and science; research may only proceed if risks to human health are minimized; participation must be voluntary and informed; and research must be appropriate, safe, and conducted with respect for human rights, dignity, and personal autonomy."⁷

The Model Law further enshrines one of the central tenets of bioethics— informed consent. Chapter Four delineates the procedures for obtaining informed consent, specifies the necessary requirements, and affirms the human right both to receive information about one's health and, notably, to refuse such information, thereby recognizing the "right not to know."

Despite its comprehensive provisions, the Model Law is advisory in nature. It was adopted by the Interparliamentary Assembly with the purpose of "facilitating the

⁷ Model Law on the Protection of Human Rights and Dignity in Biomedical Research in CIS Member States (Adopted in St. Petersburg on November 18, 2005, by Resolution 26-10 at the 26th plenary session of the Interparliamentary Assembly of CIS Member States) // Information Bulletin. Interparliamentary Assembly of Member States of the Commonwealth of Independent States. 2006. No. 37. pp. 312–326.

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coordination and implementation of harmonized legislative activities among member states on issues of common interest, and aligning national legislation with international treaties concluded within the Commonwealth as well as other international agreements.⁸

Building upon the Model Law and with the support of UNESCO, a draft federal law titled “On Biomedical Research⁹” was developed in Russia. This draft closely mirrored the provisions set forth in the Model Law. However, the legislation was never enacted; instead, the draft was returned to its initiators pending the Russian government’s position regarding the establishment and funding of a national bioethics committee. Subsequently, the bill was not resubmitted for further consideration. In 2014, a separate Model Law on the Protection of Reproductive Rights and Reproductive Health of Citizens was adopted. Article 5 of this law enumerates a comprehensive set of rights, including: “the right to reproductive choice, the right to protection of reproductive health, the right to access information and confidentiality, the right to infertility treatment, the right to family planning, the right to safe motherhood, the right to safe artificial termination of pregnancy, the right to medical sterilization, the right to gamete donation, and the right to cryopreservation and storage of gametes”¹⁰.

For a comprehensive study of legal instruments adopted within the CIS pertaining to the protection of human rights in the context of bioethics, reference can be made to the unified register of legal acts and related documents maintained by the CIS¹¹. This register contains a total of 6,836 documents spanning various subjects¹². A targeted search using the keyword “bioethics” identifies four relevant documents, among which is the 2007 Resolution on Recommendations “On Ethical and Legal Regulation and Safety of Genetic Medical Technologies in the CIS Member States” (hereinafter referred to as the Resolution), adopted by the Interparliamentary Assembly.

The Resolution was enacted with the objective of establishing foundational regulatory principles for biomedical research involving human subjects. Article 4 underscores the imperative to respect human rights and fundamental freedoms, uphold the dignity and uniqueness of the individual, and preserve the physical, mental, and genetic integrity of persons in the application of genetic technologies¹³. Article 5 affirms the prioritization of individual interests over those of society and science—a core tenet of bioethics. Additionally, Article 6 declares that “the human body, its tissues and organs, and the human genome in its natural state shall not constitute a source of

⁸ Provisions on the development of model legislative acts and recommendations of the Interparliamentary Assembly of Member States of the Commonwealth of Independent States. Adopted in St. Petersburg on April 14, 2005, by Resolution 25-8 at the 25th plenary session of the Interparliamentary Assembly of Member Nations of the CIS (as amended and supplemented on November 23, 2012) // Information Bulletin of the Interparliamentary Assembly of Member States of the Commonwealth of Independent States (IPA Information Bulletin). 2013. No. 57. Part 2. pp. 295-307 – item 1.2.

⁹ The Bill “On Biomedical Research” dated September 21, 2007, No. 471650-4 // sozd.duma.gov.ru

¹⁰ Model Law of the Interparliamentary Assembly of Member States of the Commonwealth of Independent States “On the Protection of Reproductive Rights and Reproductive Health of Citizens” (adopted at the forty-first plenary session of the Interparliamentary Assembly of Member States of the CIS (Resolution No. 41-21 of November 28, 2014)) // <https://base.garant.ru/72627980/>.

¹¹ Unified Register of Legal Acts and Other Documents of the Commonwealth of Independent States URL: <https://cis.minsk.by/reestr2/> (accessed on 30 May 2024).

¹² Hereinafter, the data is current as of May 30, 2024.

¹³ Resolution on recommendations “On ethical and legal regulation and safety of genetic medical technologies in CIS member states” dated October 31, 2007, No. 29-12 // <https://cis.minsk.by/reestr2/> . - Art. 4

income.¹⁴ Dedicated sections further elaborate on the principles of respect for human dignity and personal autonomy.

The content of the Resolution aligns with global bioethical trends and establishes a solid foundation for the regulation of human rights in biomedical research within the CIS framework. A search for the term “biotechnology” in the CIS legal register yields 108 documents; however, none pertain directly to human bio-rights. Instead, the majority address trade relations, economic cooperation, and business development.

An analysis using the phrase “human rights” identifies key legal instruments such as the CIS Convention on Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, adopted in 1995. Notably, Article 3 of this convention explicitly safeguards human bio-rights by prohibiting medical or scientific experiments without free consent, while Article 15 indirectly addresses the right to health protection. Compliance with this convention is overseen by the CIS Human Rights Commission, which produces non-binding reports on human rights promotion and protection.

Additional relevant documents within the register include the 1997 Agreement on Medical Assistance Provision to CIS Citizens, the 1992 Agreement on Cooperation in Public Health Protection, the 2007 Recommendations on Ethical and Legal Regulation and Safety of Genetic Medical Technologies, and the 2019 Recommendations on the Ethics of Nanotechnologies. While the scope of CIS regulation in bioethics is less extensive than international standards, it nevertheless encompasses a broad range of regulated relationships, with particular emphasis on protecting human rights in biomedical research. However, it is important to note that these regulations are predominantly “soft law” instruments—model laws and recommendations—and lack mandatory binding force. Furthermore, many documents date back several decades, underscoring the need for timely legislative updates in response to rapid biotechnological advances.

In contrast to the CIS’s broad cooperation mandate, the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU) was established primarily to foster economic development and integration among its members. Article 1 of the EAEU Treaty defines its objective as “ensuring free movement of goods, services, capital, and labor, while harmonizing policies across economic sectors”¹⁵. Although respect for universally recognized international legal principles is a stated foundation, the treaty itself does not explicitly reference human rights. The concept of “human” protection appears only in contexts such as sanitary regulations (Article 56) and consumer protection (Section XII).

The EAEU¹⁶ legal portal lists 417 acts related to “human rights,” all of which pertain to trade, pharmaceutical circulation, and veterinary services. The EAEU Court, tasked with ensuring uniform application of EAEU law, adjudicates disputes primarily concerning economic and entrepreneurial rights of legal entities and individual entrepreneurs. The jurisdiction of the EAEU Court encompasses, among other matters, the adjudication of applications submitted by member states concerning compliance issues, as well as claims filed by economic entities alleging violations of their rights in the sphere of economic and entrepreneurial activities. Within this framework, an economic entity is defined as either a legal person or an individual entrepreneur. It may be posited that, within the EAEU legal framework, the concept of “human rights” is not explicitly articulated in relation to natural or personal human rights. Furthermore, with regard to the focus of the present study, regulatory provisions addressing bioethical matters are notably absent from the EAEU’s scope of regulation.

¹⁴ Ibid. - Art. 6

¹⁵ Treaty on the Eurasian Economic Union (Signed in Astana on May 29, 2014) (as amended on May 25, 2023) // Official website of the Eurasian Economic Commission <http://www.eurasiancommission.org/> - para. 1 of Art. 1

¹⁶ EAEU Legal Portal URL: <https://docs.eaeunion.org/ru-ru> (accessed on 04.06.2024).

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A solitary document appears in the legal portal under the keyword “bioethics”— Recommendation No. 33 of the Eurasian Economic Commission Board titled “On Guidelines for Working with Laboratory (Experimental) Animals in Preclinical (Non-Clinical) Research.” Under the keyword “biotechnology,” 65 documents address export-import regulations, trade, and veterinary services. Thus, the EAEU’s legal regulation remains predominantly economic in nature, consistent with the union’s foundational purpose. Nevertheless, a growing body of scholars and policymakers within the EAEU advocate for broadening its legal scope to incorporate human rights protection as a complementary development vector.

The institution of human rights protection is widely recognized as a critical catalyst for deeper regional integration. Literature on integration processes emphasizes that “economic objectives are inevitably complemented by humanitarian goals”¹⁷. The universal principle of respect for human rights is foundational; without its observance, sustainable economic and social development is unattainable. The Chairman of the Eurasian Economic Commission, Vladimir Kovalev, has expressed the view that “EAEU law could become an alternative to global human rights protection systems that have lost their relevance.”¹⁸ In parallel, scholar Zh.D. Busurmanov has called for the adoption of a Eurasian Declaration of Human and Peoples’ Rights, emphasizing “the importance of *regionality* in the international protection of human rights and freedoms”. At the same time, he argues that “the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights should remain the principal global standard in this area”¹⁹.

Some researchers have advanced even further, proposing the establishment of a Eurasian Court of Human Rights²⁰. The rationale is grounded in the recognition that the current EAEU Court is severely limited in jurisdiction due to its exclusively economic mandate and restricted access for applicants. As a result, human rights remain insufficiently protected within the EAEU legal framework. While the organization’s economic orientation explains this limitation to an extent, comparative examples from other regional organizations suggest that such specialization does not preclude the development of human rights institutions.

The European Union, though initially created for economic and political cooperation, has evolved mechanisms for the protection of fundamental rights. Similarly, the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) recognizes, promotes, and protects human rights in accordance with the African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights. Global experience demonstrates that a limited institutional mandate does not prevent the creation of rights-protective mechanisms.

Specifically, with regard to the focus of this study, the EAEU has already begun regulatory activity in sensitive areas such as the pharmaceutical sector, where ethical and human rights considerations, particularly bioethical ones, are unavoidable. This indicates the growing relevance of human rights protections within the EAEU’s evolving regulatory scope. In this context, the creation of a human rights court within the EAEU could provide institutional protection for fundamental rights in areas linked to its competence.

¹⁷ Khuzihanova, A.R. Judicial Mechanism of International Organizations of Regional Economic Integration. Abstract of dissertation for the degree of Candidate of Juridical Sciences. Kazan. 2018. p. 11.

¹⁸ EAEU law could become an alternative to global human rights protection systems that have lost their relevance // Website of the Eurasian Economic Commission URL: <https://eec.eaeunion.org/news/pravo-eaes-moglo-by-stat-alternativoy-utrativshim-svoyu-aktualnost-globalnym-sistemam-zashchity-prav/> (accessed on 05.06.2024).

¹⁹ Busurmanov, Zh. D. The Eurasian Economic Union as a New Humanistic Value // Journal of Foreign Legislation and Comparative Law. 2014. No. 4(47). Pp. 619–621.

²⁰ Alternatively, the Human Rights Collegium at the EAEU Court.

Proponents of this idea point to several enabling conditions: “the existence of supranational legal structures, an established system of EAEU governance bodies, and deepening economic cooperation that may naturally evolve into social and humanitarian harmonized legal integration”²¹.

However, the proposal to establish a separate human rights court within the EAEU raises concerns regarding institutional relevance and feasibility. The establishment of a separate human rights body requires the adoption of a legally binding instrument in this area. From this study’s perspective, a more appropriate and viable pathway lies in the development of human rights institutions within the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS). The CIS has already laid foundational groundwork in this area, including the Convention on Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, which—though limited in scope—explicitly protects certain bioethical rights. In contrast, the EAEU has no corresponding legally binding human rights instrument. Furthermore, human rights are largely absent from its legal discourse, being referenced only in the context of sanitary, consumer, or trade regulation. Let us compare the composition of these two organizations. Some states, namely Russia, Armenia, Belarus, Kazakhstan, and Kyrgyzstan, are members of both organizations. Therefore, if the Eurasian Convention on Human Rights is adopted, the question of competition between the two conventions will arise. In addition, the CIS is more focused on comprehensive cooperation, not limited to economic matters.

Notably, Speaker of the Federation Council of the Russian Federation, Valentina Matvienko, has voiced support for the creation of a unified human rights court within the CIS framework²². In line with this position, this study proposes that the CIS strengthen its human rights protection mechanisms, particularly by adopting a legally binding instrument specifically focused on bioethics. This document should codify the principles of biolaw, define related human rights, and impose obligations on both states and third parties to observe and implement these rights in national legislation. Additionally, the establishment of a judicial body for the protection and promotion of human rights in the field of bioethics is recommended. Such an institution would serve as a regional enforcement mechanism, capable of addressing violations and interpreting bioethical principles in a consistent legal framework.

Thus, the regulation of bioethical issues within post-Soviet intergovernmental organizations remains underdeveloped. Initial steps have been taken—particularly within the CIS—with the adoption of the Convention on Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms and advisory documents such as the Model Law “On the Protection of Human Rights and Dignity in Biomedical Research in CIS Member States.” However, the non-binding nature of these instruments limits their effectiveness. In contrast, the EAEU has not addressed human rights in its legal framework at all, and issues of bioethics remain entirely unregulated.

To address these gaps, we proposed that the CIS adopt a legally binding act on the protection and promotion of human rights in the field of bioethics. This act should require full implementation by member states and serve as the foundation for establishing a regional court with competence over bioethical and broader human rights issues.

This initiative is of particular relevance to the Russian Federation, especially in light of regional integration processes in which it is actively involved. The significance is primarily underscored by its withdrawal from the Council of Europe in March 2022 and its cessation of participation in the European Convention on Human Rights as of

²¹ Millerov, E.V., Chupilkin, Yu.B. The Eurasian Court of Human Rights as an analogue of the ECHR // Russian Judge. 2022. No. 6. Pp. 55–59.

²² Speaker of the Federation Council V. Matvienko allowed for the creation of a single human rights court for the CIS // CIS Internet portal URL: <https://e-cis.info/news/566/99257/> (accessed on 05.06.2024).

September 16, 2022. Since that date, the European Court of Human Rights has no longer had jurisdiction to consider new complaints from Russian individuals.

Conclusion

The development of bioethics is an inevitable response to the rapid advancement of biomedical technologies. Its primary task today is to establish a comprehensive framework for the protection and promotion of human rights in this context, as well as to mitigate threats to those rights. Central to bioethics are fundamental principles such as the dignity and autonomy of the individual and the principle of voluntary, informed consent to medical interventions.

Bioethics functions as a social regulator that requires legal support through binding regulations to effectively govern social relations and guarantee human rights protections. Biolaw, an emerging independent branch of law, embodies a unique synthesis of moral and legal norms. It features the institution of “human biolaw” and recognizes a special subject composition whereby the individual simultaneously serves as a subject, object, and beneficiary of legal regulation. Furthermore, biolaw acknowledges collective subjects, including humanity at large and future generations.

At the universal level, regulation is extensive and diverse, with numerous resolutions and the extensive body of documents enacted to protect and promote human rights within the field of bioethics. The General Assembly, ECOSOC, WHO, UNESCO, and other international bodies adopt resolutions addressing various general and specific aspects of biolaw, which serve as sources of soft law. However, the efficacy of these non-binding norms in ensuring effective human rights protection remains questionable. Although some principles may eventually acquire customary status and binding force, we contend that it is premature to assume comprehensive enforcement. There is a pressing need to establish supervisory bodies capable of monitoring compliance and promptly addressing violations.

The Council of Europe’s human rights system offers a noteworthy model of an enforcement mechanism, though it too requires refinement. It is recommended that all Council of Europe member states gradually accede to the Convention on the Protection of Human Rights and Dignity of the Human Being with regard to the Application of Biology and Medicine, extending the jurisdiction of the European Court of Human Rights to cover its provisions. This aligns with the broader lesson from the European Union experience that economic integration is intrinsically linked to respect for and protection of human rights.

Within the context of post-Soviet intergovernmental organizations, the regulation of bioethical issues remains insufficiently effective. We propose that the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) consider adopting a legally binding act that regulates the protection and promotion of human rights in bioethics, with obligatory implementation in national legislation. Additionally, the establishment of a judicial body dedicated to human rights—particularly bio-rights—should be pursued.

Comparative analysis of Russian legislation versus international standards reveals a number of issues that warrant consideration by the Russian legislator regarding patient prioritization and the extent of protection afforded to personal dignity. Nevertheless, our national law already enshrines a wide range of human rights and guiding principles in biolaw.

Internationally, legal regulation of bioethics is still in its infancy. While numerous documents addressing various biomedical domains and human rights have emerged, these instruments alone are insufficient for comprehensive protection and promotion of bio-rights.

A major deficiency is the lack of a binding international treaty specifically dedicated to bioethics and human rights. We advocate transferring this issue to the regional level. Similarly, there is a need to establish regional human rights monitoring,

supervisory, and judicial bodies to ensure state compliance with bioethical standards. It is our view that these matters should be addressed within the framework of regional integration, as this approach would foster enhanced cooperation among states and promote a unified set of goals and values.

Another significant gap is the absence of a universally accepted classification of human bio-rights analogous to established categories of civil, political, social, economic, and cultural rights. Achieving consensus on this matter remains challenging, given divergent perspectives in science, philosophy, religion, and society at large. Bioethics and related human rights are a very sensitive issue. This complexity underscores the sensitivity of bioethics and the practical necessity of regional regulatory approaches grounded in universal UN recommendations.

Moreover, evolving biotechnological capabilities continuously reshape our understanding of the human being, their life, and rights—extending questions of regulation to pre-birth and post-mortem stages. Novel legal considerations are emerging, such as property rights over cryopreserved cells and labor rights associated with surrogate motherhood or clinical drug testing. Addressing these developments demands the gradual evolution and reconceptualization of law and jurisprudence to ensure agile and effective responses to the ethical and legal challenges posed by biotechnological progress.

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